

Condensation of Glutaryl Chloride, Pimelyl Chloride, Suberyl Chloride, Azeloyl Chloride and Sebasoyl Chloride with Aromatic Hydrocarbons

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[Glutaryl chloride, Pimelyl chloride, Suberyl chloride, Azeloyl chloride and Sebasoyl chloride have been condensed with toluene, *o*-chloro toluene, *o*-xylene, *m*-xylene, chlorobenzene and bromobenzene in the presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride yielding 1 : 7, 1 : 8, 1 : 9 and 1 : 10 diketones together with small amount of ω -keto acids in some cases.]

The condensation of glutaryl chloride, pimelyl chloride, suberyl chloride and azeloyl chloride with the aromatic hydrocarbons was found to occur smoothly at 0-5° in the presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride leading to the formation of diaryl diketones (I) in good yield together with the aryl keto acids (II) in small quantity in some cases.

The constitution of the products is established by their oxidation with alkaline potassium permanganate to the corresponding benzoic acid or phthalic acid derivatives.

The homogeneity of the products of condensation was evidenced from *TLC* on microchromatoplate using silica gel "G" as adsorbent and iodine as indicator.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

General procedure : Freshly distilled hydrocarbon (25 ml) was placed in a three-necked flask (250 ml) fitted with a mechanical stirrer, a dropping funnel and a calcium chloride guard tube and cooled to 0°. Anhydrous aluminium chloride (4g.) was added to this cooled hydrocarbon. The aliphatic dibasic acid dichloride (1 ml.) diluted with the hydrocarbon (10 ml.) was added dropwise under stirring during a period of one hour. After the addition of the acid chloride was complete, the mixture was stirred vigorously for a further period of three hours at room temperature and allowed to stand overnight at this temperature. After being decomposed with ice-cooled hydrochloric acid, the product was distilled in steam

to remove excess of hydrocarbon. The crude product solidified on cooling. This was filtered off and treated with NaHCO_3 solution when a portion of it remained insoluble. The alkali insoluble residue was collected by filtration, washed with water and crystallised.

Treatment of the NaHCO_3 -soluble portion: The aqueous alkaline solution was acidified with HCl when the keto acid separated out. The crude product was crystallised.

The compounds, obtained from hydrocarbons and dibasic acid dichlorides, are described in Table 1 and Table 2.

TABLE I
Condensation of Aromatic Hydrocarbons with Glutaryl Chloride, Pimelyl Chloride and Suberyl Chloride

Aromatic Hydrocarbons	Acid Chloride used	Products formed	Formulae	Analysis Found %	Analysis Required %	Derivatives	Remarks
Toluene	1) Glutaryl Chloride	a) 1,5 bis-(<i>p</i> -toluyl)-pentane 1,5 dione, m.p. 115-17° (ethanol)	$C_{13}H_{20}O_2$ (I, R = H; R ₂ = CH ₃ ; n = 3)	C; 81.42 H; 7.13	81.40 7.58	2 : 4 D.N.P.H., m.p. 260° (ethyl acetate) [Found : N, 17.12 ; C ₃₁ H ₂₈ O ₈ N ₈ requires N, 17.50%]	
		b) γ - <i>p</i> -toluyl butyric acid, m.p. 155° (dil. methanol)	$C_{12}H_{14}O_3$ (I, R = H; R ₂ = CH ₃ ; n = 3)	C; 69.99 H; 6.94	69.90 6.79	Semicarbazone, m.p. 215° (decomp.) (ethanol) [Found : N, 15.72 ; C ₁₃ H ₁₇ O ₃ N ₃ requires N, 16.0%]	
	2) Pimelyl Chloride	a) 1,7 bis-(<i>p</i> -toluyl)-heptane 1,7 dione, m.p. 95° (ethanol)	$C_{21}H_{24}O_2$ (I, R = H; R ₂ = CH ₃ ; n = 5)	C; 81.69 H; 7.62	81.81 7.79	2 : 4 D.N.P.H., m.p. 237-38° (benzene) [Found : N, 17.03 ; C ₃₃ H ₃₂ O ₆ N ₆ requires N, 16.77%]	Oxidation of the diketone with alkaline KMnO ₄ gave terephthalic acid.
		b) ω -(<i>p</i> -toluyl)-hexanoic acid, m.p. 130° (hot water)	$C_{14}H_{18}O_3$ (II, R = H; R ₂ = CH ₃ ; n = 5)	C; 71.73 H; 7.92	71.80 7.69	—	—
	3) Suberyl Chloride	a) 1,8 bis-(<i>p</i> -toluyl)-octane 1,8 dione, m.p. 118° (ethanol)	$C_{22}H_{26}O_2$ (I, R = H; R ₂ = CH ₃ ; n = 6)	81.75 7.84	81.98 8.07	2 : 4 D.N.P.H., m.p. 146° (ethanol) [Found : N, 16.76 ; C ₃₄ H ₃₄ O ₈ N ₈ requires N, 16.43%]	Oxidation of the diketone with alkaline KMnO ₄ gave terephthalic acid. Infrared spectrum (nujol) ν max (cm ⁻¹) 1675 ; 1603 ; 826.
		b) ω -(<i>p</i> -toluyl)-heptanoic acid, m.p. 106° (dil. ethanol)	$C_{13}H_{20}O_3$ (II, R = H; R ₂ = CH ₃ ; n = 6)	72.41 7.85	72.57 8.06	—	—

TABLE 1 (Contd.)

Aromatic Hydrocarbons	Acid Chloride used	Products formed	Formulae	Analysis Found %	Analysis Required %	Derivatives	Remarks
<i>o</i> -Chloro toluene	1) Pimetyl Chloride	a) 1, 7 bis-(3-methyl, 4-chloro phenyl)-heptane 1, 7 dione, m.p. 82° (ethanol)	$C_{21}H_{22}O_2Cl_2$ [I, R = H; R ₁ = CH ₃ ; R ₂ = Cl; n = 5]	C; 66.62 H; 5.71	66.85 5.84	Dioxime, m.p. 164° (ethanol) [Found: N, 6.42; C ₂₁ H ₂₂ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂ requires N, 6.88%]	Oxidation of the diketone with alkaline KMnO ₄ yielded 4-chloro isophthalic acid, m.p. 293°. The homogeneity of the diketone was evidenced from a single spot in TLC (Rf 0.6) using chloroform as developer. Infrared spectrum (nujol) ν max (cm ⁻¹); 1684; 1588; 820.
		b) ω -(3-methyl, 4-chloro benzoyl)-hexanoic acid, m.p. 136° (dil. ethanol)	$C_{15}H_{17}O_3Cl$ [II, R = H; R ₁ = CH ₃ ; R ₂ = Cl; n = 5]	C; 62.36 H; 6.09	62.57 6.33	—	Infrared spectrum (nujol); ν max (cm ⁻¹); 1700; 1665; 1575; 820
	2) Suberyl Chloride	a) 1, 8 bis-(3-methyl, 4-chloro phenyl)-octane 1, 8 dione, m.p. 105° (ethanol) n = 6]	$C_{23}H_{26}O_2Cl_2$ [I, R = H; R ₁ = CH ₃ ; R ₂ = Cl; n = 6]	C; 67.38 H; 6.01	67.51 6.14	Dioxime, m.p. 158° (ethanol) [Found: N, 6.41; C ₂₃ H ₂₆ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂ requires N, 6.65%	The diketone on oxidation yielded 4-chloro isophthalic acid, m.p. 293°. The homogeneity of the diketone was evidenced from a single spot in TLC (Rf 0.6) using chloroform as developer.
		b) ω -(3-methyl 4-chloro benzoyl)-heptanoic acid, m.p. 106° (dil. ethanol)	$C_{15}H_{19}O_3Cl$ [II, R = H; R ₁ = CH ₃ ; R ₂ = Cl; n = 6]	C; 63.57 H; 6.83	63.72 6.73	—	—
Chloro-benzene	1) Glutaryl Chloride	*1, 5 bis-(<i>p</i> -chloro phenyl)-pentane 1, 5 dione, m.p. 125° (ethanol) (m.p. of the compound prepared by Skraup and Guggenheimer (Ber., 1925, 58, 2488) is 117°	$C_{17}H_{14}O_2Cl_2$ [I, R = R ₁ = H, R ₂ = Cl; n = 3]	C; 63.30 H; 4.37	63.5 4.36	2; 4 D.N.P.H., m.p. 230-31° [Found: N, 19.7; C ₂₅ H ₂₂ O ₆ N ₈ Cl ₂ requires N, 20%]	Oxidation of the diketone with neutral KMnO ₄ yielded <i>p</i> -chloro benzoic acid, m.p. 236°.

TABLE I (Contd.)

Aromatic Hydrocarbons	Acid Chloride used	Products formed	Formulae	Found %	Analysis Required %	Derivatives	Remarks
2) Pimelyl Chloride	Pimelyl Chloride	1, 7 bis-(<i>p</i> -chloro-phenyl)-heptane 1, 7 dione, m.p. 109° (ethanol)	$C_{19}H_{18}O_2Cl_2$ [I, R = R ₁ = H; R ₂ = Cl; n = 5]	C; 65.17 H; 5.29	65.33 5.16	2 : 4 D.N.P.H., m.p. 212-13° (benzene) [Found : N, 16.00; C ₃₁ H ₂₆ O ₈ N ₆ Cl ₂ requires N, 15.80%]	Oxidation of the diketone with alkaline KMnO ₄ yields <i>p</i> -chloro benzoic acid, m.p. 236° Infrared spectrum (nujol) : ν max (cm ⁻¹) ; 1667 ; 1625 ; 1580 ; 860 ; 815.
3) Suberyl Chloride	Suberyl Chloride	<i>ω</i> -(<i>p</i> -chlorobenzoyl) hexanoic acid, m.p. 134-35° (dil. ethanol)	$C_{13}H_{15}O_3Cl$ [II, R = R ₁ = H; R ₂ = Cl; n = 5]	C; 61.09 H; 5.75	61.30 5.89	—	Infrared spectrum (nujol) ν max (cm ⁻¹) 1700 ; 1670 ; 1582 ; 820.
o-Xylene	1) Pimelyl Chloride	<i>ω</i> -(<i>p</i> -chlorobenzoyl)-heptanoic acid m.p. 110° (ethanol)	$C_{20}H_{20}O_2Cl_2$ [I, R = R ₁ = H; R ₂ = Cl; n = 6]	C; 65.88 H; 5.42	66.12 5.51	2 : 4 D.N.P.H., m.p. 248-49° (benzene) [Found : N, 15.01, C ₃₂ H ₂₈ O ₈ N ₆ Cl ₂ requires N, 15.49%]	On oxidation with alkaline KMnO ₄ , the diketone yielded <i>p</i> -chloro benzoic acid, m.p. 236°
o-Xylene	1) Pimelyl Chloride	<i>ω</i> -(<i>p</i> -chlorobenzoyl)-heptanoic acid m.p. 110° (ethanol)	$C_{14}H_{17}O_3Cl$ [II, R = R ₁ = H; R ₂ = Cl; n = 6]	C; 62.36 H; 6.21	62.58 6.33	2 : 4 D.N.P.H., m.p. 91° (ethanol) [Found : N, 12.16, C ₂₀ H ₂₁ N ₄ O ₆ Cl requires N, 12.48%]	Infrared spectrum (nujol) ν max (cm ⁻¹) ; 1692 ; 1670 ; 1582 ; 810.
o-Xylene	1) Pimelyl Chloride	1, 7 bis-(3, 4 dimethyl phenyl)-heptane 1, 7 dione or phenyl)-heptane 1, 7 dione, m.p. 98° (ethanol)	$C_{23}H_{28}O_2$ [I, R = H; R ₁ = R ₂ = CH ₃ ; n = 5] $C_{23}H_{28}O_2$ [I, R = R ₁ = CH ₃ R ₂ = H; n = 5]	C; 81.92 H; 8.08	82.15 8.33	2 : 4 D.N.P.H., m.p. 228° (benzene) [Found : N, 15.66; C ₃₅ H ₃₆ O ₈ N ₆ requires N, 16.09%]	—
o-Xylene	1) Pimelyl Chloride	<i>ω</i> -(3, 4 dimethyl benzoyl) hexanoic acid or <i>ω</i> -(2,3 dimethyl benzoyl) hexanoic acid, m.p. 137° (dil. ethanol)	$C_{15}H_{20}O_3$ [II, R = H; R ₁ = R ₂ = CH ₃ ; n = 5] or $C_{15}H_{20}O_3$ [R = R ₁ = CH ₃ ; R ₂ = H; n = 5]	C; 72.36 H; 8.19	72.57 8.06	—	Infrared Spectrum (nujol) ν max (cm ⁻¹) ; 1700 ; 1670 ; 1587 ; 823.

TABLE I (Contd.)

Aromatic Hydrocarbons	Acid Chloride used	Products formed	Formulae	Analysis Found %	Analysis Required %	Derivatives	Remarks
<i>o</i> -Xylene	2) Suberyl chloride	1, 8 bis-(3, 4 dimethyl phenyl) octane 1, 8 dione or 1, 8 bis-(2, 3 dimethyl phenyl)-octano 1, 8 dione, m.p. 121° (ethanol) [I, R = R ₁ = CH; R ₂ = H; n = 6] or C ₂₄ H ₃₀ O ₂ [I, R = R ₁ = CH; R ₂ = H; n = 6]	C; 82.04 H; 8.61	82.28 8.57	Dioxime, m.p. 170° (ethanol) [Found: N, 7.15. C ₂₄ H ₃₂ O ₂ N ₂ requires N, 7.37%]	The diketone was found to be very resistant towards oxidation with alkaline KMnO ₄ and chromic acid. It yielded a well defined single spot in TLC (Rf. 0.8) using chloroform as developer and silica gel "G" as adsorbent.	
<i>m</i> -Xylene	1) Glutaryl Chloride	b) ω -(3, 4 dimethyl benzoyl)-heptanoic acid or ω -(2, 3 dimethyl benzoyl)-heptanoic acid, m.p. 91° (dil. ethanol)	C ₁₆ H ₂₂ O ₃ (II, R = H; R ₁ = R ₂ = CH ₃ ; n = 6) or C ₁₆ H ₂₂ O ₃ (II, R = R ₁ = CH ₃ ; R ₂ = H; n = 6)	C; 73.08 H; 8.16	73.28 8.40	—	—
<i>m</i> -Xylene	1) Glutaryl Chloride	* 1, 5 bis [2, 4 dimethyl phenyl]-pentane 1, 5 dione, m.p. 75° (ethanol) reported m.p., 60.61° (Borsche, <i>Ber.</i> , 1919 52, 2077.)	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ O ₃ (I, R = CH ₃ ; R ₁ = H; R ₂ = CH ₃ ; n = 3)	C; 81.32 H; 7.5	81.68 7.79	Dioxime, m.p. 135° (dil. ethanol) [Found: N, 8.5; C ₂₁ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₂ requires N, 8.28%]	—
Bromobenzene	1) Glutaryl Chloride	a*) 1, 5 bis-(<i>p</i> -bromophenyl)-pentane 1, 5 dione, m.p. 152° (ethanol)	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ O ₂ Br ₂ (I, R = R ₁ = H; R ₂ = Br; n = 3)	C; 50.27 H; 3.45	49.75 3.41	2: 4 D.N.P.H., m.p. 201.2° (ethanol) [Found: N, 18.92; C ₂₃ H ₂₂ O ₂ N ₂ Br ₂ requires N, 19.21%]	The diketone on oxidation with neutral KMnO ₄ yielded <i>p</i> -bromo benzoic acid, m.p. 255°.
		b*) <i>p</i> -bromo benzoyl butyric acid, m.p. 129-130° (dil. ethanol)	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₃ Br (I, R = R ₁ = H; R ₂ = Br; n = 3)	C; 48.51 H; 4.40	C; 48.71 H; 4.06	—	—

* The compounds marked with (*) have been prepared in collaboration with Nirendra Nath Chakravarti.

TABLE I (Contd.)

Aromatic Hydrocarbons	Acid Chloride used	Products formed	Formulae	Analysis Found %	Analysis Required %	Derivatives	Remarks
2)	Pimelyl Chloride	1, 7 bis-(<i>p</i> -bromo phenyl)-heptane 1, 8 dione, m.p. 138°, (glacial acetic acid)	$C_{19}H_{16}O_2Br_2$ ($L, R = R_1 = H$; $R_2 = Br$; $n = 5$)	C ; 51.93 H ; 4.29	52.17 4.11	Dioxime, m.p. 198° (ethanol) [Found : N, 6.32 ; $C_{19}H_{20}O_2N_2Br_2$, requires N, 5.98%]	The diketone on oxidation yielded <i>p</i> -bromo benzoic acid, m.p. 255°.
3)	Suberyl Chloride	a) 1, 8 bis-(<i>p</i> -bromo phenyl)-octane 1, 8 dione, m.p. 174° (glacial acetic acid)	$C_{20}H_{20}O_2Br_2$ ($L, R = R_1 = H$; $R_2 = Br$; $n = 6$)	C ; 52.86 H ; 4.18	53.10 4.42	Dioxime, m.p. 165° (dil. ethanol)	On-oxidation with alkaline $KMnO_4$ the diketone yielded <i>p</i> -bromo benzoic acid, m.p. 255°.
		b) ω -(<i>p</i> -bromo benzoyl) heptanoic acid, m.p. 119° (dil. ethanol)	$C_{14}H_{17}O_3Br$ [$L, R = R_1 = H$; $R_2 = Br$; $n = 6$]	C ; 53.46 H ; 5.23	53.68 5.43	—	—

TABLE 2
Condensation of Aromatic Hydrocarbons with Azeloyl chloride and Sebasoyl Chloride,

Aromatic Hydrocarbons	Acid Chloride used	Products formed	Formulae	Analysis Found %	Analysis Required %	Derivatives	Remarks
Toluene	1) Azeloyl Chloride	a) 1, 9 bis-(<i>p</i> -toluyl) nonane 1, 9 dione, m.p. 82° (ethanol)	$C_{23}H_{26}O_2$ (I, R = R ₁ = H; R ₂ = CH ₃ ; n = 7)	C; 81.89 H; 8.48	82.15 8.35	2 : 4 D.N.P.H, m.p. 207° (glacial acetic acid)	On oxidation with alkaline KMnO ₄ , the diketone yielded terephthalic acid
		b) ω-(<i>p</i> -toluoyl) octanoic acid m.p. 98° (dil. ethanol)	$C_{16}H_{22}O_3$ (II, R = R ₁ = H; R ₂ = CH ₃ ; n = 7)	C; 73.15 H; 8.47	73.28 8.40	—	—
o-chloro toluene	1) Azeloyl Chloride	a) 1, 10 bis-(<i>p</i> -toluyl) decane 1, 10 dione, m.p. 103° (ethanol)	$C_{24}H_{30}O_2$ (I, R = R ₁ = H; R ₂ = CH ₃ ; n = 8)	C; 82.11 H; 8.33	82.28 8.57	2 : 4 D.N.P.H, m.p. 230-32° (d) (benzene)	On oxidation, the diketone yielded terephthalic acid.
		b) ω-(<i>p</i> -toluyl) nonanoic acid, m.p. 109° (dil. ethanol)	$C_{17}H_{22}O_3$ (II, R = R ₁ = H; R ₂ = CH ₃ ; n = 8)	C; 73.77 H; 8.74	73.91 8.69	—	—
		a) 1, 9 bis-(3-methyl-4-chloro phenyl)-nonane 1, 9 dione m.p. 94° (ethanol)	$C_{23}H_{26}O_2Cl_2$ (I, R = H; R ₁ = CH ₃ ; R ₂ = Cl; n = 7)	C; 67.93 6.22	68.14 6.42	—	On oxidation the diketone formed 4-chloro isophthalic acid, m.p. 292°. The diketone yielded a well defined single spot in TLC (Rf 0.6) using silica gel "G" as adsorbent and a mixture of benzene and chloroform (2 : 1) as developer which proved its homogeneity.

TABLE 2 (contd.)

Aromatic Hydrocarbons	Acid Chloride used	Products formed	Formulae	Analysis Found %	Analysis Required %	Derivatives	Remarks
<i>o</i> -chloro toluene	Azeloxy Chloride	<i>b</i>) ω -(3-methyl, 4-chloro benzoyl)-octanoic acid, m.p. 118° (dil. ethanol)	$C_{16}H_{21}O_3Cl$ (II, R = H; R ₁ = CH ₃ ; R ₂ = Cl; n = 7)	C; 64.57 H; 6.84	64.76 7.08	—	—
	Sebasoyl Chloride	<i>a</i>) 1, 10 bis-(3-methyl 4-chloro phenyl)-decane 1, 10 dione, m.p. 118° (glacial acetic acid)	$C_{24}H_{28}O_2Cl_2$ (I, R = H; R ₁ = CH ₃ ; R ₂ = Cl; n = 8)	C; 68.57 H; 6.44	68.74 6.68	2 : 4 D.N.P.H., m.p. 245°(d) (glacial acetic acid) [Found : N, 14.01 $C_{26}H_{36}O_6N_6Cl_2$ requires N, 14.37%]	On oxidation with alkaline KMnO ₄ , the diketone yielded 4-chloro isophthalic acid, m.p. 233°.
Chlorobenzene	1) Azeloxy Chloride	<i>a</i>) 1, 9 bis-(<i>p</i> -chloro-phenyl)-nonane 1, 9 dione m.p. 105° (dil. ethanol)	$C_{21}H_{22}O_2Cl_2$ (I, R = H; R ₁ = H; R ₂ = Cl; n = 7)	C; 66.61 H; 5.62	66.85 5.84	Dioxime, m.p. 98° (dil. ethanol) [Found : N, 6.85 $C_{21}H_{24}O_2N_2Cl_2$ requires N, 6.87%]	On oxidation with alkaline KMnO ₄ , the diketone yielded <i>p</i> -chloro benzoic acid, m.p. 236°.
		<i>b</i>) ω -(<i>p</i> -chloro benzoyl) octanoic acid, m.p. 130° (dil. ethanol)	$C_{15}H_{19}O_3Cl$ (II, R = R ₁ = H; R ₂ = Cl; n = 7)	C; 63.55 H; 6.63	63.72 6.73	—	—
	2) Sebasoyl Chloride	1, 10 bis-(<i>p</i> -chloro phenyl)-decane 1, 10 dione	$C_{22}H_{24}O_2Cl_2$ (I, R = R ₁ = H; R ₂ = Cl; n = 8)	C; 67.45 H; 5.96	67.51 6.14	2 : 4 D.N.P.H., m.p. 245° (glacial acetic acid) [Found : N, 14.73, $C_{24}H_{32}O_6N_6Cl_2$ requires N, 14.91%]	On oxidation with alkaline KMnO ₄ , the diketone yielded <i>p</i> -chlorobenzoic acid, m.p. 236°

TABLE 2 (Contd.)

Aromatic Hydrocarbons	Acid Chloride used	Products formed	Formulae	Analysis Found %	Analysis Required %	Derivatives	Remarks
<i>o</i> -Xylene	1) Azeloyl chloride	a) 1, 9 bis-(3, 4 dimethyl phenyl) nonane 1, 9 dione or 1, 9 bis-(2, 3 dime-thyl phenyl)-nonane 1, 9 dione, m.p. 106° (ethanol)	$C_{25}H_{32}O_2$ (I, R = H; $R_1 = R_2 = CH_3$; $n = 7$) or $C_{25}H_{32}O_2$ (I, R = $R_1 = CH_3$; $R_2 = H$; $n = 7$)	C; 81.96 H; 8.53	82.22 8.79	Dioxime, m.p. 128° (dil. ethanol)	The diketone was found to be resistant towards oxidation with alkaline $KMnO_4$ or chromic acid. The homogeneity of the diketone was established by TLC using silica gel 'G' as adsorbent (R_f 0.5) and chloroform as developer.
	2) Sebasoyl chloride	1, 10 bis-(3,4 dime-thyl phenyl)-decane 1, 10 dione m.p. 141° (ethanol) or 1, 10 bis-(2, 3 dime-thyl phenyl)-decane 1, 10 dione m.p. 141° (ethanol)	$C_{26}H_{34}O_2$ (I, R = H; $R_1 = R_2 = CH_3$; $n = 8$) or $C_{26}H_{34}O_2$ (I, R = $R_1 = CH_3$; $R_2 = H$; $n = 8$)	C; 82.28 H; 8.76	82.54 8.99	2 : 4 D.N.P.H., m.p. above 250° (benzene) [Found : N, 15.50 $C_{26}H_{34}O_2 \cdot N_8$ requires N, 15.17%]	The diketone was found to be resistant towards oxidation and could not be oxidized with alkaline $KMnO_4$ or chromic acid. The homogeneity of the diketone was evidenced from a single spot in TLC (R_f 0.5) using a benzene-chloroform mixture (2 : 1) as developer and silica gel 'G' as adsorbent. Infrared spectrum (nujol) ν_{max} (cm^{-1}); 1660; 1625 1590; 878, 820.
Bromobenzene	Azeloyl chloride	1, 9 bis-(<i>p</i> -bromophenyl)-nonane 1, 9 dione, m.p. 129° (glacial acetic acid)	$C_{21}H_{22}O_2Br_2$ (I, R = $R_1 = H$; $R_2 = Br$; $n = 7$)	C; 53.85 H; 4.51	54.08 4.72	Dioxime, m.p. 114° (ethanol) [Found : N, 5.32 $C_{21}H_{24}O_2N_2Br_2$ requires N, 5.65%]	On oxidation with alkaline $KMnO_4$ the diketone produced <i>p</i> -bromo benzoic acid, m.p. 255°

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